

CAPITAL EFFICIENCY MANAGEMENT OF COMPANIES
AND ITS SPECIFIC FEATURES

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6066258>

Usmonov B.

Tashkent State University of Economics

Abstract: *This article describes the scientific and theoretical aspects of capital efficiency management of companies. Additional to this, capital efficiency theory and its important factors and directions are given to value the capital efficiency of company. Moreover, problems related to capital efficiency of company with its solutions are given .*

Keywords: *capital, efficiency, management, company, value of capital.*

Despite various levels of macroeconomic and financial problems, globalization and the impact of the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, the practice of rapidly developing countries depicts that investment decisions made by financial managers of companies are made by different investors. one of the most optimal ways to manage the capital efficiency of a company in assessing the investment potential of companies and increasing capital efficiency, as well as in the implementation of investment projects, is its need.

In addition, as a result of the growth of investment flows to companies, the introduction of a method of managing the capital efficiency of companies and determining the level of impact on private and debt capital, which are factors affecting the capital of companies, as well as financial indicators shows the need to develop a new approach to determining its share in capital and determining the rational composition of capital.

World practice confirms that in order to assess the business value of companies in developed countries, first of all, its capital efficiency is becoming one of the necessary conditions in terms of managing and ensuring its investment attractiveness.

A number of economists have conducted research on capital efficiency, most notably western economists John R., Graham and Campbell R. and Harvey survey which was in 2001, taken into 392 U.S. companies from which 73.5 percent of financial managers described capital asset management as an important part of a company's investment attractiveness [1]. In particular, foreign economists Dirk Brunen, Eybe de Yong, and Keys Codecs, based on the above analysis, found that in 2004, almost 45% of financial managers in 313 major European companies took assets as a primary source of determining the company's capital value and efficiency, taking into account its share in capital [2].

Another economist, Aswath Damodaran [3], focused on the practice of valuing capital value of companies, arguing that the expansion of business and investment opportunities of the enterprise, in turn, leads to an increase in the value of capital. He also expressed the view that the growth of debt and private capital could ensure an increase in the value of the company's capital. In this case, the value of private capital for investors

indicates the reserve capacity of the enterprise to repay its obligations to creditors, while the value of debt capital indicates the probability of default risk of the enterprise. Debt and equity are the main sources of financing for an enterprise's investment project.

Among the local economists, Professor R. Karlibaeva [4] in her research noted that in determining the rational composition of the capital of joint-stock companies should take into account the following three types of hypotheses. First of all, it is necessary for joint-stock companies to take into account the value of their capital in attracting private capital and debt capital, in particular, this process is closely related to capital efficiency. Second, the high level of debt capital of joint-stock companies indicates a low level of economic profitability of joint-stock companies. As a third hypothesis, the determination of the capital structure of joint-stock companies will be inextricably linked to the level of development of financial instruments in the public financial market.

When evaluating a company's capital efficiency, a number of factors are taken into account, in particular equity and debt capital, the increase in the value of private equity is related to the tax rate and the D / E (debt to equity ratio) ratio of equity to debt capital. The idea put forward by economists Modiglian and Miller also shows how to choose a company's rational capital composition. The specific features of this theory are as follows: First, it is necessary to minimize transaction costs when achieving the ideal financial market activity, which is to some extent free from shortcomings. Second, management costs should not increase significantly as the company's financial position is an indicator of positive and sustainable growth. Third, there should be opportunities to borrow and lend at the level of return on low-risk assets in the financial market. Furthermore, Modiglian and Miller argue that a change in the composition of an enterprise's capital does not affect its efficiency, regardless of the tax rate in the process of assessing the value of a company's capital and its efficiency. At the same time, it was noted that the increase in the value of private capital has a positive correlation with the D / E (debt to equity ratio) ratio of debt capital.

From the above, it can be concluded that joint stock companies of developed countries, in addition to managing the efficiency of capital, use a number of methods to assess its value.

The main criterion for this is the development of financial markets in developed countries, including the widespread use of financial instruments in the formation of capital of joint stock companies. Today in our country there are a number of problems in the management of capital efficiency of joint-stock companies, and we believe that the following measures should be taken:

First, joint-stock companies need to adapt to the standards of evaluation of developed countries in the management of capital efficiency. This will serve to assess the business environment in the country and increase capital efficiency and strategic management.

Secondly, it would be expedient to harmonize the national standards of our country with the principles of assessment standards of developed countries. Doing so, in turn, will allow to determine the investment potential of the joint-stock company and the level of risk in the country and to determine the capital risk of the joint-stock company.

REFERENCES:

1. Graham, J.R. and Harvey, C.R (2001) “The theory and practice of corporate finance: evidence from the field”, *Journal of Financial Economics* 60, 187-243
 2. Dirk Brounen, Abe de Jong and Kees Koedijk (2004) “Corporate Finance In Europe Confronting Theory With Practice”, erim report series research in management, 1-44
 3. <http://people.stern.nyu.edu/adamodar/pdfiles/papers/costofcapital.pdf>
 4. Structure of the capital and financial stability of the enterprises in condition of modernization of economics. Oct 20, 2020
-

